

A NEW APPROACH TO LOW COST MANUFACTURING OF ADVANCED STRUCTURES

ADRIAAN BEUKERS

DELFT UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY
Faculty of Aerospace Engineering
THE NETHERLANDS

ABSTRACT

In this paper the attention is focused on the improvement of the almost classical concept of honeycomb sandwich structures. This attractive concept has been subject of a rejuvenation study. Three aspects were of special interest:

- * the increase of the mechanical efficiency and durability per unit mass,*
- * the simple production of plate materials and integrated shell structures without cost, quality and weight penalties.*
- * and in addition the integration of acoustical damping and thermal isolation without weight increase,*

INTRODUCTION

In aerospace engineering there is an ever continuing urge to improve the efficiency of propulsion, of lift generation and of the airframe itself. It is well known that the application of materials with better high-temperature characteristics per unit mass can improve the propulsion efficiency considerably. Refined aerodynamics influence both the efficiency of propulsion, and the efficiency of the lift generating surfaces. Higher lift to drag ratios in all stages of flight can be realized by new configurations of wings and stabilizers and by increase of the slenderness and smoothness in 3-dimensions.

The need to cut down the direct operating costs (DOC) is the important reason for improving the structural efficiency. It can be reached by lowering the structural weight and the production and maintenance costs of the airframe. Modern anisotropic and continuous structural concepts, lacking the appearance of artificiality and handwork, are very promising in this respect. They not only offer interesting improvements of the static strength, stiffness and durability per unit mass. They also yield a very easy and direct way of improving the efficiency by getting rid of the structural discontinuities, as they are found in the nowadays light-alloy, multi-components assemblies (Fig. 2).

These assemblies are constructed from an immense number of different parts, inefficiently jointed to each other, painted and sealed afterwards in order to get sufficient protection against an ever penetrating environment.

A look back into the history of powered flight shows that the "life-time" of an airframe technology tends to increase, reflecting the increased capabilities of material and structural sciences extracting the maximum from typical structural solutions. However, in general when a technological "life-cycle" is reaching the end, marginal improvements, both in production costs and in structural efficiency, can only be realized by huge intellectual and financial investments.

Stiffened plate and shell structures are interesting examples of this phenomenon (Fig. 1).

Yet, what finally remains is:

- * limited structural efficiency
- * cost and capital intensive manufacturing
- * cost and capital intensive maintenance

A look back also reflects that the airworthiness requirements become increasingly heavy which makes the introduction of new materials and structural concepts increasingly difficult. It should be kept in mind, however, that compared to the billions of years of earth life evolution, where insects already fly around for 300 million of years and men started playing a role 20 million years ago, 100 years of airframe development is only a start. Probably at the level of "Engineering Neanderthaler". In fact the application of anisotropic, continuous structures is nothing but a natural, logical, following step in airframe evolution. In the present paper a qualitative explanation has been given how these structures can be realized and what their potentials are, keeping in mind the arguments of costs and efficiency.

Fig. 1: Mass reduction in history (Northrop) and in a foreseen future (ref. 1) Clearly is shown the ending life times of several materials and/or manufacturing technologies

CONTINUITY: SANDWICH SHELL STRUCTURES

Although the concept of sandwich structures is known very well, it has been scarcely applied in the period that stiffened plate concepts were in full development. The lack of non-corrosive structural core-materials, difficult bonding techniques and the difficult integration of local reinforcements, made a breakthrough of sandwiches in primary structures unlikely. Nowadays difficult expensive production methods and several structural load limiters still act as thresholds for more wide application. Premature failures can occur, induced by a whole family of secondary effects, most of them based on the vulnerable, poorly controllable skin-honeycomb connection, which in fact is formed by a small fillet of adhesive material.

Most structures which are composed from smaller parts fail before reaching the overall, global, failure mode. Local failures occur, sometimes in primary areas, where concentrated loads are introduced. Mostly they occur in unexpected areas. This almost fundamental behaviour is not dependent on the composition of the structure and on the materials used. The reason is the structural discontinuity, which is frequently present in structures composed of plates, doublers, stiffeners and frames. It is also present, although more difficult to distinct, in integrally machined and in laminated composite structures. Therefore successful designing of efficient and durable structures is mainly an art, a skill in avoiding discontinuities, both in strength (the weakest link in a chain) and, much more tricky, in stiffness (stress concentrations, singularities).

Fig. 2:
Inplane continuity as
counterpart of stiffening
with discrete plate elements.

In composite honeycomb structures discontinuities can be minimized in the inplane directions (Fig. 2). However, one enormous discontinuity remains, namely the facesheet to coreweb connection in transverse direction. A very thin fillet of adhesive material acts as an intersection between the "inplane load carrying" facesheets and the thinwalled "transverse load carrying" honeycomb core. The individual elements of a sandwich act very poor in bending, inplane compression and lateral shear. Once closely jointed together, they do quite the opposite, thanks to a short circuit formed by a thin, non filling, almost brittle fillet of adhesive. It is obvious that the previously mentioned problems, resulting from a poor connection between the individual elements of a sandwich can be avoided by the application of a more continuous joint. Such a joint occurs for example in sandwiches with a continuous thermoset foamcore.

In order to make use of both the high specific mechanical properties of honeycomb core-materials and the advantage of a continuous elastic foundation, a homogeneously filling adhesive is needed with a high volume (contact surface) per unit mass (low density). A hot melt adhesive with an in-situ foaming capability fulfills these requirements. If the usual epoxy film adhesive or resin rich ply is replaced by such a hot-melt film of a compatible engineering plastic and an equivalent thickness or weight, the original thickness increases 10 to 25 times during the curing cycle, in this way extending the contact area between core and facesheet enormously. In general there is no weight penalty and when core shear buckling or core compression was a dominating factor for the mechanical behaviour of the original sandwich, the former core can even be replaced by a lighter version.

Fig. 3
Foaming thermoplastics applied in structural and non-structural sandwiches: continuity in transverse direction.

In this way a synthesis is reached by using the high specific strength and stiffness of honeycomb cores and the continuity of a flexible and filling engineering foam.

Apart from the improvement of the structural efficiency and the durability per unit mass, the following features are also very noticeable:

- * higher impact and compression resistance (floor panels, leading edges),
- * improved acoustical and thermal isolation (fuselage sections),
- * no water ingress (all exterior parts, interior service areas).

and even more important,

- * a low cost production process at atmospheric pressure and moderate curing temperatures (vacuum & oven)
- * no close tolerances needed (gap filling adhesive)
- * easy local filling or potting (edges, loaded areas)
- * crushed core techniques for structural applications (edges, cut outs)
- * easy jigless bending in case of thermoplastic facesheets (folded structures).

REALISATION: FOAMING HOT-MELT ADHESIVES

Several groups of thermoplastics offer temperature and chemical resistant materials in film form, which can be used as hot-melt adhesive with foaming capability:

polyarylens, PEK and PEEK,
 polysulfones, PES,
 polyimides, PI and PEI,

more specific:

Table 1: Polymers		T _{glass} °C	T _{melt} °C
Polyimide	PI	310-376	-
Polyethersulfon	PES	230	-
Polyetherimide	PEI	215	-
Polysulfon	PSU	190	-
Polyetherketon	PEK	167	360
Polyetheretherketon	PEEK	143	340
Polyphenylensulfide	PPS	88	290
Polycarbonate	PC	150	-
Polyamide	PA	50	265
Polyethylenterephalate	PET	80	255
Polybutylenterephthalate	PBT	40	223

The foaming capability at certain temperatures can be realised by blending of the polymers with suitable blowing agents (Table 2).

Blending or compounding of polymers with additives is generally based on mechanical mixing techniques. The resulting blend has an appearance varying from granules, powder to paste, depending on the initial physical form of the components (chips, granules, powders or liquids).

Table 2: Blowing agents	Density kg/dm ³	Boiling Point °C	Blowing efficiency rank
Pentanes	0.62	36	11
Hexanes	0.66	65	10
Heptanes	0.68	90	12
Benzene	0.87	80	8
Dichloromethane	1.33	40	3
Trichloromethane	1.49	61	7
Tetrachloromethane	1.58	77	9
Methanol	0.79	65	1
Ethanol	0.79	78	2
2-propanol	0.78	82	5
Acetone	0.79	56	4
Methyl ethyl ketone	0.81	80	6

However, for the application of a foaming thermoplastic as an adhesive for sandwiches and for reasons of blending, transport, storage and usage, the film is an ideal form. A thermoplastic film can be blended rather easily by transporting it through a fully saturated environment of a suitable physical blowing agent until the desired agent content is reached (Fig. 4).

The process can be accelerated by elevating the process parameters temperature and/or pressure. The production volume per hour is depending on the polymer film thickness, the required agent content, the nature of both elements and on the process parameters. The result can be a stable, homogeneous blended film which in general can be stored without special conditioning. Selection of the polymers and blowing additives is based on the processability and by engineering and environmental requirements.

Fig. 4:

The most obvious criteria for a proper choice are:

- compatibility with the adherends, skins and core
- acceptable processing parameters with respect to the adherend materials
- the foam must have a rigid, closed cell structure and it must be completely stable from a mechanical, a physical and a chemical point of view
- no toxic or corrosive outgassing is allowed
- a high chemical and moisture resistance is required
- an in service temperature range from - 55°C up to 120°C
- for usage in the interior of aircraft the latest flameability, smoke and toxicity requirements must be fulfilled
- blowing capability must be present.

The blowing effectivity of the blend is controlled by the agent content and cure temperature; it must cover the following range of densities:

3, 6, 9lb/ft³

or in SI units 48, 96, 144kg/m³

These densities refer to the Nomex honeycomb range as it is used in the aircraft nowadays;

3 lb/ft³ - for aerodynamic loaded exterior parts like fairings, radomes and control surfaces,
- for interior parts like ceilings and sidewalls

6 lb/ft³ - for underseat floor panels, luggage bins and galleys

9 lb/ft³ - for entrance areas, aisle floor panels, bulkheads and locally in the areas where concentrated loads occur.

THE MANUFACTURING OF STRUCTURES

As indicated in the previous chapter, the application of foaming hotmelt adhesive films can simplify the production of smooth sandwich shell structures, even the large ones, considerably. Instead of a complicated autoclave or hot press cure cycle, a very short period of heating in an oven is sufficient. Manufacturing at low pressure (0.8 bar) and a moderate temperature (170°C)* using subcomponents with "easy" tolerances are important features of the process. A more simple and a more controllable production is almost impossible.

Although this technology seems to be a natural partner for fibre reinforced thermoplastic sandwich structures, it is also very suitable for other manufacturing techniques. Compatibility and processing studies have already shown very promising results. For instance the classical fibre reinforced epoxy laminates and the aluminium sheet laminates known as ARALL, can be synthesized with metallic or non-metallic honeycomb core materials, by applying appropriate foaming polymer films.

The development target is the production of complete sandwich shell structures, like fuselage and wing. They will have skins with varying thicknesses and lay-ups and include non-prismatic cores of various core materials and densities, combined with various foamed polymers, unfilled or locally reinforced with short fibres or micro balloons of appropriate materials. Almost every mechanical, chemical, thermal and acoustical loading, acting within the load-envelopes of subsonic aircrafts, can be matched by tuning the material composition carefully.

In case of metallic or thermoset structures, the facesheets generally must be prepared and preformed in advance. For continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastics both preforming and coforming, even of double curved areas, can be done during hot pressing. Moreover: drapeability studies and detail testing at the Delft University showed an almost unlimited out of plane forming capability of continuous FRthP plate materials without wrinkles. So, when too steep gradients in out of plane directions are avoided, curved solid edges, cut out areas, dimples, joggles and bends can even be pressed simultaneously.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In the present paper a new method for the production of sandwiches is described. An important feature of the new method is the use of foaming thermoplastic film as an adhesive between core and faces. The resulting sandwich has many potentials in terms of fabrication simplicity, cost effectiveness, mechanical efficiency and applications. It even makes integrally made complete structures as fuselages and wings conceivable.

Preliminary studies showed excellent fabrication and mechanical characteristics in combination with good acoustical and thermal properties.

Future research will be emphasized on:

the processing of films, the processing and forming of integrally structures and structural engineering related items, such as the effects of defects and cut outs, crash and impact energy absorption, all at component level.

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